

NEW CONSTITUTION DEVELOPMENT COMMUNITY

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Abstract: This article discusses the implementation of the Constitution and its articles, amendments and additions to the articles of the new version of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: Constitution, law, democratic, legal system, law, Independence, people's heritage, state development

“The Constitution is a people's state,
the basis of sustainable development and prosperous life!”

After Independence, our country reached its highest heights. It got its own state flag, coat of arms, anthem and Constitution. Peace and independence is a great happiness for us. Why do you say? - because living a peaceful and peaceful life in a beautiful and unique homeland, enjoying its clean and pure water, living under the sky, studying carefree is an example of our true happiness and peace.

The Constitution and its articles are a clear example of peace, stability, fair decision-making, continuity of our independence, youth activity, living with the times. Our independence, the peace of our country directly depends on the Constitution.

Constitution (Latin: *constitutio* - structure, constitution) is the basic law of the state. It defines the structure of the state, the system of power and management bodies, their authority and the order of their formation, the electoral system, the rights and freedoms of citizens, as well as the judicial system. The Constitution is the basis of all current laws. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted on December 8, 1992 at the XII - XI - session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic. The Constitution consists of a Preamble, 6 sections, 26 chapters, and 128 articles, in all of which justice is a priority, that is, the rights and duties of citizens of our Republic, adolescents and minors are clearly defined. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was created in harmony with the history, culture, national traditions, values, age-old traditions, cultural heritage of the Uzbek people, rooted world experience, universally recognized

international legal norms and rules. Since this day, the youth of every Uzbekistan has been following the laws of our Constitution. His every decision is important for us. The Constitution is not just a set of laws, but a solution to the problems among the youth of the population, which is important in the life of every person, has played an important role throughout our lives, and continues to be implemented. Our Constitution, which is the constitution of our country, is being served for the future generation. We should not just wait for our life to pass away, but leave a great name for ourselves. Everyone should remain a positive character in the lives of others, be a worthy child of our independent Uzbekistan, and follow the Constitution and its laws without any opposition. After that, our country will flourish, the way for the future will be opened, and it will have the strength and energy to do great things.

The Constitution states that everyone has the right to freedom and privacy. According to it, no one is allowed to be kept in prison without the basis of law. Nothing is decided outside of the law. There is an answer for every work done. Also, everyone will sincerely try to achieve peace and stability.

The constitution defines the democratic factors of the development of the state and society, and it states that the people are considered to be the only source of state power. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan has supreme legal power: the president adopts decrees, decisions and orders that are binding on the entire territory of the republic based on the Constitution and laws and in connection with their implementation. It can be said with confidence that the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a high example of the political and legal thinking of our people.

On the basis of our constitution, the national legal system, state bodies, and civil society were formed in our country. All were entitled to free education. Everyone started to live carefree in their little house. Protests and crisis are over. Everyone has the right to vote. Every person is defined as equal. Today, extensive reforms are being implemented in all areas. Our socio-economic, political and military potential is increasing, and the outlook of our citizens is increasing. All this is, first of all, the result of the life-giving power of our head dictionary.

Everyone knows that the referendum was canceled in our country in order to update and amend the Constitution. In the national referendum held on April 30, 2023, our people showed their high political consciousness, legal culture and worldview and adopted the new version of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The new version of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan created a solid foundation for the stable development of statehood, socio-political, socio-economic and legal spheres. The newly revised constitution consists of

Preamble, Section 6, Chapter 27, and 155 articles. 90.21% of the citizens who participated in the referendum held on April 30, 2023 voted in favor of our newly revised Constitution. This, in turn, is a clear indication that our people's hopes and aspirations for the establishment of New Uzbekistan are reflected in our General Dictionary. We established our Constitution together with our people. This true recognition was specially emphasized in the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the preparation and celebration of the Constitution Day of the Republic of Uzbekistan, signed on November 16, 2023.

We know that the previous version of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted on December 8, 1992 by the people of Uzbekistan in the form of their authorized representatives, that is, by the members of the parliament, the deputies of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In contrast to this, the new version of the Basic Law of our country was accepted by the people of Uzbekistan directly through a direct vote in a national referendum. In this sense, the true author of the newly revised Constitution of Uzbekistan is the people. The will of citizens is the source and driving force of reforms.

The first paragraph of Article 7 of the new version of the Constitution stipulates the norm that “the people are the only source of state power”. In the form of this norm, the universally recognized principle of people's power, that is, the principle that the people are the bearer of sovereignty and the only source of state power, is established in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In particular:

First of all, New Uzbekistan will be a state where human dignity and worth, rights and freedoms, and legal interests are of the highest value;

secondly, the people should serve the people, not the public authorities;

thirdly, people want to see positive changes in their lives today, not tomorrow or in the distant future, and therefore, “living with people's concerns”, fulfilling the legitimate demands and wishes of our people should become the most important criterion for evaluating the activities of state bodies;

fourthly, “the people should be the sole source and author of the law”, that is, all important decisions should be made with the participation of the population, on the basis of consultation with civil society institutions. That is the demand and advantage of democracy. The President of the Republic, the Parliament and the government must adhere to these requirements. In this regard, the following issues:

ensuring human rights;

strengthening the role of parliament and political parties, civil society institutions, mass media in deepening democratic reforms and modernization of the country;

reforming the state administration system, increasing the role of the parliament in the system of restraining and balancing the branches of power;

special attention will be paid to improving the quality and efficiency of public services, strengthening the accountability and transparency of the activities of public bodies, and the practical implementation of parliamentary and public control mechanisms.

Undoubtedly, these norms serve not only to strengthen the constitutional and legal foundations of people's power in our country, but also to ensure the will of our people and the legitimate interests of people. To put it more clearly, in our country, the generally recognized principle mentioned above: "the people should serve the people, not the state bodies, the state bodies should serve the people" is strictly followed.

At this point, it should be noted that on May 8, 2023, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the implementation of the new Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted. This important document requirements:

full implementation of our newly revised Constitution;

- implementation of the priority principles established in it in harmony with the grand idea of New Uzbekistan;

- leaving the activity of state bodies alone in the new constitutional and legal conditions;

- aimed at ensuring that citizens clearly feel the spirit of the Constitution in their lives.

As stated in the decree, the new version of the Constitution, based on its supreme legal force, is directly and unconditionally applicable to the activities of state bodies and organizations, including courts and law enforcement agencies. The strict and consistent implementation of new, modern and very important norms included in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular, the direct enforcement of these constitutional provisions by the courts, has started a new era in the history of our country and people in terms of glorifying human rights, freedoms, legal interests and dignity. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted, Human value is not some abstract, lofty concept for us. By human dignity, we mean, first of all, the peaceful and safe life of every citizen, the provision of his fundamental rights and freedoms.

In short, I am a representative of this nation, I am considered a child. I rejoice in every success, I share in every pain, every representative is dear to me, for better or for worse, he is my compatriot. In a word, today in our country, all sectors are developing rapidly. We should

effectively use the main opportunities that lie ahead of us and make a worthy contribution to the development of our dear Motherland, Uzbekistan.

Today, it can be stated with confidence that the main focus of the new norms of our Constitution is on ensuring the stable development of a person, society and the state. With the adoption of the new version of the Basic Law, a more solid constitutional and legal basis was created in this regard. The positive constitutional experience of countries located in Europe, Asia, East and America regions is reflected in our constitution. Our basic law was carefully organized by legal scholars, political scientists, experts of many international organizations. We are sure that, as the representatives of international organizations and experts have pointed out, the adoption of the new version of the Constitution of Uzbekistan, based on the principle of human dignity and dignity, has created a solid foundation for further improving the well-being of the people, and for the rapid development of people, civil society and the state.

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